

SUTIKA PARICHARYA IN AYURVEDA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF POSTNATAL CARE

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ABSTRACT

The Ayurveda Science give importance role to the care of mother and her life especially in ANC (antenatal) and PNC (postnatal care). A postnatal period is starting immediately after the separation of placenta and extending up to six weeks, called as puerperium or puerperal period. Postnatal care is named as Sutika Paricharya in Ayurvedic classics. Garbhini and Sutika Paricharya are very well Detail described by our Ayurvedic Samhitas. Sutika Paricharya refers to the specialized postnatal care regimen described in Ayurvedic classics for women after childbirth. The postpartum period is critical due to physical strain, blood loss, and aggravation of Vata Dosha. Ayurvedic texts outline dietary regulations, lifestyle modifications, therapeutic interventions, and herbal formulations to restore strength, promote lactation, prevent complications, and ensure

long-term reproductive health.

KEYWORDS: Sutika Paricharya, Post natal care, Prasava, Ahara Vihara, Puerperium.

INTRODUCTION

The postpartum period (Sutika Kala) begins immediately after delivery and continues until restoration of the mother's health. Childbirth causes depletion of Rakta, Dhatus, and Ojas along with aggravation of Vata Dosha. Therefore, systematic postnatal care is essential for proper recovery.

A woman becomes special after she becomes a mother. Ayurveda emphasizes much importance to the care of women especially in the prenatal and postnatal period. A woman who has just given birth to a child followed by expulsion of placenta is called as Sutika.^[1] During puerperium the body tissues, specially the pelvic organs revert back approximately to pre-pregnant state both anatomically and physiologically.

After delivery the woman become emaciated and have Shunya Shareera because of Garbha Vriddhi, Sithila Sarva Shareera Dhatu, Pravahana Vedana, Kleda Rakta Nisruti, Agni Mandya, these will lead to Dhatu Kshaya. hence extra care to be given to prevent complication during this period to avoid Sutika Rogas which can happen in this period if not managed properly. Acharyas said that Sutika Rogas are difficult to cure and sometimes are incurable.^[2] Ayurveda has advised a specific diet and lifestyle regimen called Sutika Paricharya to prevent further complications and restore the health of mother.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is a conceptual study. Data on sutika paricharyais gathered from classics and organized in a systemic manner.

Sutika Kal

ACHARYA	SUTIKA KALA
Acharya Charak	Sutika kal is not exactly mentioned
Acharya sushruta	1 ½ months
Ashtang sangraha	1 ½ months or up to recurrence of menses
Ashtang Hridaya	1 ½ months or up to recurrence of menses
Acharya Kashyap	6 months
Acharya Bhavaprakash	1 ½ months or up to recurrence of menses
Acharya Yogratnakar	1 ½ months or up to recurrence of menses
Modern- Immediate	Within 24 hours
Early	Up to 7 days
Remote	Up to 6 weeks

Principles of Sutika Paricharya

- Vata Shamana
- Agni Deepana
- Dhatu Poshana
- Pachana
- Rakta vrudhhi
- Stanya vrudhhi

- Gharbhashaya shodhan
- Koshta shodhan

Sutika Paricharya

The Sutika is described in Ayurvedic texts with a particular mode of a stipulated period. The sarva shareera dhatu of mother will be in sheetilaavastha because of growth and development of fetus in her. This is further added by Pravahana Vedana and Kleda Raktha srava during delivery. Hence the woman is with Shunya Shareera because of Prasava vedana and she is prone to Sutika rogas. The Sutika Paricharya itself helps in punar navikarana of her body. Hence Sutika Paricharya not only supports the women but also prevents Sutika rogas. After delivery there is vitiation of Vata, expulsion of fetus, loss of fluid, and exhaustion during labour are responsible for Dhatukshaya and during this period even a minor ailment can cause a lot of harm to the body. In Sutikakala many complications can occur as described in Ayurveda about 74 diseases can occur during this period. So Sutika must be given more attention to prevent these complications.

Ahara

Samhita	Ahara
Charak Samhita	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ghrita, taila vasa, majja medicated with pippali (piper longum linn), Pippalimula chavya (piper retrofractum Vahl) • Chitraka, shunthi, Susnighdha yavagu (liquid gruel of rice) medicated with above mentioned drug for • Aapyayna (vrnhana chikitsa)
Sushruta Samhita	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sneha yavagu or kshira yavagu medicated with drugs of Vidarigandhadi gana from 3rd or 4th to 6th or 7th day. • Meat soup of wild animals medicated with Yava, • Kola, Kulatha cooked with Sali rice from 7th or 8th day to Sutika kala
Ashtang sangraha	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liquid Yavagu prepared with either milk or drugs of vidarigandhadi gana for 3, 5 or 7 days • Yusha of yava, Kola, Kulatha from 4th, 6th or 8th day to 12th day • Laghu ahara (light diet) • Meat soup wild animals (jangal mamsarasa)
Ashtang Hridaya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panchkola churna along with ghrita or taila • Usna gudodaka or vataharu aushadhi saadhita peya for 2 to 3 days • Vidarigandhadi gana sidha snehyukta yavagu or kshira yavagu from 4th or 7th day • Brimhana diet from 8th to 12th day • After 12th day meat soup should be used

Vihara

Samhita	Vihara
Charak Samhita	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snehapana (consumption of fat) Abhyanga (massage) with taila or ghrita. • Udarveshtana (abdominal tightening) • Parishechana (hot water pouring)
Sushruta Samhita	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abhyanga (massage) with Bala taila. • Parishechana (hot water pouring) with or vatahara aushadhisiddha kwatha. • Dushashonitshuddhi by taking Pippali, Pippalimula, Hastapippali, chitraka, srngabera with ushna gudodaka • Woman should avoid anger, exercise and coitus
Ashtang sangraha	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abhyanga (massage) with bala taila • Snehapana (consumption of fat) • Udarveshtana(abdominal tightening) after massage of abdomen with taila or ghrita. • Parisechana with ushnodaka (hot water pouring) in morning and evening before sneha and yavagu pana

DISCUSSION

- In Sutika Agni is Manda hence Agni Deepana drugs should be used for few days immediately after delivery, prior to the administration of Brimhana drugs. The drugs which are used instantly after delivery are Agni Vardhaka by their nature,
- Use of Snehana suppresses Vata.
- Uttama Rasa produces Uttama Stanya which depends on quality of Agni.
- Yava, Kola, Laghu Annapana is advised after 5 days, this form of food helps to replenish Dhatu.
- Mamsa Rasa, Madhura Dravyas, Jeevaniya and Brimhaniya Dravyas might act as Dhatu Vardhaka and helps to maintain proper lactation.
- Abhyanga recommended with Bala Taila might help to restrain vitiated Vata Dosha.
- Parisechana by using Kwatha prepared by Vatahara Dravyas act as Vedanahara, Kleda Hara.
- Udara Patta Bandhana wrapping the abdomen with long and clean cloth, which in turn helps abdomen to retrieve its normal position and there is no accumulation of Vata in vacant sites.
- Dhupana as Rakshoghna, Vedanahara should be given by using Kustha, Guggulu, Agaru.
- To prevent the complaints during Sutika Kala such as Pristha Shoola, Kati Shoola, Yoni Vedana, Adhamaan, Prajagarana, Trishna etc. Sutika Paricharya is needed.

CONCLUSION

Sutika Paricharya is a comprehensive postpartum care protocol described in Ayurveda. Its emphasis on diet, lifestyle regulation, therapeutic interventions, and mental well-being makes it valuable for maternal recovery and complementary to modern obstetric care.

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